

INTERACTION BETWEEN INDIVIDUAL AND CORPORATE WORK LIFE BALANCE STRATEGIES AND THEIR ASSOCIATIONS WITH SUBJECTIVE WELLBEING : EVIDENCE FROM RMG SECTOR OF BANGLADESH

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Abstract

This research aims to identify if and how individual and organizational Work Life Balance (WLB) strategies are associated with the perception of Subjective wellbeing (SWB) of Readymade Garments (RMG) workers in Bangladesh. For this study, 241 samples from the RMG sector of the country have been selected and data was collected through structured questionnaire. Ordinary Least Square (OLS) regression has been conducted to investigate the relationship among the perception of work life balance and subjective wellbeing of the target group. Results show that Timing, Tempo, Role Conflict, and interaction between individual and organizational WLB positively enhance WLB of Bangladeshi RMG workers. The study also found significant positive relationship among (a) workers' beliefs about his/her own satisfaction with life, and (b) autonomy to set his/her own roster with affective Subjective Wellbeing (SWB) of the RMG workers of the country. On the contrary, role conflict was found to have a negative effect on SWB. Interestingly though, the effect of WLB has been found to have no significant effect on the SWB in the RMG workers of Bangladesh. Moreover, composite scores of WLB and SWB show that the workers' work and life are moderately balanced and overall, they are dissatisfied with their lives. Wide scale adoption of relevant WLB supportive activities, building awareness to develop effective individual as well as organizational WLB strategies by both the corporates and the Government, and rigorous psychological training will ensure collective wellbeing of the workers in Bangladesh ensuring an environment of 'decent work' in this sector catalyzing Bangladesh's efforts to go one step closer towards achieving SDG 8 (Decent work for all). This research also offers an extensive guideline about the most relevant individual and organizational WLB strategies to improve WLB status as well as the happiness of the RMG workers of the country. This study also offers a wide range of future research opportunities and policy directions to both the RMG managers and the Government of Bangladesh.

Keywords : *Work-life balance (WLB), Subjective wellbeing (SWB), Individual WLB strategy, Organizational WLB strategy, Satisfaction with life scale (SWLS)*

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1. INTRODUCTION

Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) were adopted in 2015 by all member countries of the United Nations with the primary objective of ensuring poverty eradication, protection of the planet and offering peace and prosperity for all living human beings by 2030 (UNDP, 2019). SDG 8 focuses on promoting a “Sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, productive employment and decent work for all” and aims at ensuring full as well as productive employment along with decent work for all men and women alike (United Nations, 2019). This paper attempts to look at the interaction among individual and organizational strategies to achieve Work-Life Balance (WLB) and their associations with subjective wellbeing (SWB) of individuals working in the RMG sector of Bangladesh. This paper also looks at the degree to which one’s satisfaction with life as measured through the Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWLS) affects the aforementioned relationship (Diener et al., 1985). Curiosity about this issue is obvious given that achievement of WLB and a good SWB at the micro level catalyzes common wellbeing of the workers at the macro level (one of the agendas of ‘Decent Work’ specified by ILO and included in SDGs) assisting a country to achieve SDG 8 (United Nations System Chief Executives Board for Coordination; International Labour Office, 2008).

WLB indicates the extent to which people’s involvement and satisfaction are balanced between family and work (Greenhaus & Singh, 2003; Gregory & Milner, 2009). Work life integration, on the contrary, is a broader concept and is defined as the capability of individuals to combine or, integrate work and family responsibilities effectively with as minimum conflict as possible (Clark, 2000; Wheatley, 2017). In personal life of every individual there exists a range of commitments, duties and responsibilities, which changes over the course of his/her life. In most cases, family occupies the largest part of one’s life. Therefore, researchers favor integration rather than just a balance between work and life (Fagan et al., 2012). However, there are limitations in work-life integration literatures. A few of them are summarized in Feigon et al. (2018). They are: (a) the construct of work/life is not consistent (b) there is a scarcity of research related to evidence-based recommendations and (c) population of study is limited to gender, ethnicity, professional field, phases of profession (Feigon et al., 2018). Moreover, it is imperative that work-life conflict, also the starting point of the Work-Life integration, is the flipside of work-life balance. Therefore, it is unnecessary to separately focus on these issues. In this study, the primary focus is on work-life balance (WLB), rather than work-life integration (WLI) and work-life conflict (WLC).

Work-family conflict, often defined as inter-role conflict, refers to the fact that work and life roles are incompatible to each other (Carlson et al., 2000; Greenhaus & Beutell, 1985). Research on this issue further reveals the fact that such conflict affects psychological distress, job satisfaction, organization commitment, turnover and life satisfaction (Carlson et al., 2000; Frone et al., 1992; Higgins et al., 1992; O’Driscoll et al., 1992; Parasuraman et al., 1989). Only work-life balance could relieve stress,

increase job satisfaction, reduce turnover and improve life satisfaction (Antai et al., 2015; Anttila et al., 2015; Gröpel & Kuhl, 2009; Wheatley, 2017; Zheng et al., 2015). Work-life balance provides implied support to the philosophy of Quality of Work Life (QWL), which states that people are the primary resource of an organization and they must be treated with dignity and respect (Tabassum et al., 2011). Therefore, the authors of this article are motivated to check if garments workers of Bangladesh have work-life balance (WLB) and consequently enjoy a satisfied life or not. If they do, it implies that their organizations are also living by the principles of QWL.

This research focuses on the workers of RMG sector in Bangladesh and their WLB, SWB as well as Satisfaction with life (SWL) status. Bangladesh has made a remarkable progress in terms of economic and social indicators. Bangladesh is one of the fastest growing economies in the world with an average GDP growth of appx. 7%. The Bangladesh apparel industry is one of the major engines of economic growth in Bangladesh. The industry contributes over 11% of the GDP and employs over 4 million workers, of whom majority are women. The RMG sector contributes to 83.9% of export in Bangladesh, making it the largest contributor to FX reserves in the FY 2017-18 (Ovi, 2018; Shahajada Mia & Masrufa Akter, 2019). There are many instances in the past those point fingers to the quality of life (both family and work) and earnings related problems of Bangladeshi RMG workers as major reasons for labor unrests in the sector (Islam & Siengthai, 2009; Weber-Steinhaus, 2019).

Previous studies have focused individually on wellbeing of the workers (Hasan et al., 2017), relationships among supervisor behavior, compensation and benefit and work-life balance (Rubel & Kee, 2014), individual mechanisms to tackle WLC issues (Akter, 2013) and factors affecting QWL (Marium Akter, 2018). However, there are no studies focusing on the interaction among factors affecting WLB (antecedents), individual and organizational WLB strategies, work-life balance and subjective wellbeing. This paper aims to fill that void by investigating how work-life balance interacts with one's own perception about his/her personal wellbeing in the garments industry of Bangladesh.

1.1 Objectives of the Study

This study attempts to determine the relationship between WLB variables, WLB, Individual and corporate WLB strategies, and interaction between individual and organizational WLB with SWB of the RMG workers of the country. It also attempts to determine the WLB, SWB and SWLS statuses of the aforesaid group.

1.2 Key Research Questions

- (a) What is the current WLB status of the workers in Bangladeshi textile and RMG sectors?
- (b) What is the state of affective SWB and SWL of the textile and RMG workers in Bangladesh?

- (c) How do WLB variables affect overall WLB status of the RMG workers in Bangladesh? To what extent do the interaction between individual and organizational WLB affect overall WLB status?
- (d) What individual WLB strategies are of significant importance to balance work and lives of the people in RMG and textile sectors of Bangladesh?
- (e) Do the interactions among individual and corporate WLB policies affect the affective SWB of the RMG workers of the country?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This section of the paper reviews the literature on work-life balance and the variables to be used in the study.

2.1 Factors Affecting WLB

Characteristics of work and life both affect an individual's personal life and are predictors of work-life balance (Antai et al., 2015). Therefore, variables for both work and family domains are important to understand underlying forces affecting work-life balance.

2.2 Temporal and Spatial Flexibility

Time flexibility has been increasingly getting attention of the researchers in analysis of quality of work-life and work-life balance (Messenger, 2011). A 5-day working week, 8 hours of working time during a day, free evenings, weekends, annual holidays and time flexibilities for work have become common practices in modern organizations (Anttila et al., 2015; Craig & Powell, 2011; Fagan et al., 2012; Rapoport & Le Bourdais, 2008; Supiot, 1999). Remote working as well as flexibility and autonomy in setting own working hours have both positive and negative consequences in theory and in practice. Prior research shows that employees have a tendency to exert additional effort in work if they are allowed to set their own working hours (Anttila et al., 2015; Kelliher & Anderson, 2008). Long working week, unsocial working hours, high working time tempo generally have negative association and autonomy has positive association with work-life balance (Grzywacz & Marks, 2000). Working time tempo reflects intensity of working time (Adam, 1995; Anttila et al., 2015; Fagan et al., 2012).

As far as spatial flexibility is concerned, it is heavily argued and debated that spatial flexibility may have impact on satisfaction, child care and family wellbeing of employees (Anttila et al., 2015; Felstead et al., 2002). However, contradictory arguments are also present. Working from home may interfere with relationships between employees with their personal time, family relationships (Such as, relationship with partner) and relationships with children (Anttila et al., 2015; Maruyama & Tietze, 2012; Sullivan, 2012).

2.3 Role Conflict

According to role theory, an individual experiences greater stress, dissatisfaction and inefficiency in work if that individual's behavior is inconsistent to the expectations imposed on him/her (Rizzo et al., 1970). As it is implied in Gregory and Milner (2009), role conflict can be further elaborated as the role overload created by the imposed expectations from both work and family (Gregory & Milner, 2009). Role conflict, in this study, is measured through Rizzo, House, and Lirtzman's (1970) eight-item measure of role conflict (which includes FOUR dimensions of role conflict) (Carlson et al., 2000; Rizzo et al., 1970).

The major dimensions of role conflict, as mentioned earlier, are discussed below:

(a) Person – role Conflict:

It is the conflict between an individual's own internal values and defined role behavior (Kahn et al., 1964; Rizzo et al., 1970).

(b) Intra – role Conflict:

It is a conflict between an individual's actual and defined role behavior created by scarcity of time, resources or capabilities created by another person of a related role. It can be termed as intra-sender conflict from the other person's perspective. On the contrary, from the point of view of the individual concerned, it is an intra-role or person-role conflict (Gross et al., 1958; Rizzo et al., 1970).

This conflict can be created for several reasons. One such reason is explained by Kahn et al. (1964) who mentioned that people at different roles send communications to a focal person, who himself/herself is in a role. If these communications are not compatible and two or more than two of such incompatible communications are sent, compliance for the focal person would become a problem creating what had already been termed as intra-sender conflict earlier on (Kahn et al., 1964; Shumate & Fulk, 2004). It is implied that this conflict may arise from work as well as from home, such as: spouse vs. parent.

(c) Inter – role conflict or role overload:

Sometimes an individual needs to perform several roles which may require that individual to act differently based on situations. Such incompatible behavior, which is a function of situation, can be defined as role overload or, inter-role conflict (Gross et al., 1958; Rizzo et al., 1970).

2.4 Unsocial Working Hour and Autonomy

Antai et al. (2015), on the contrary, looked only at temporal and spatial flexibilities across different countries using the following variables such as: work hours, unsocial work hours, autonomy, work-time intensity and workplace flexibility. Results show that in all the countries, all the variables had negative relationship with good work-life balance except for need fulfillment (Anttila et al., 2015). However, working time flexibility does not affect employees of every country similarly. Lott (2015) conducted

a working-time flexibility survey on UK, Sweden, Germany and the Netherlands and found that employees of both genders from Netherlands and Sweden were more benefited from working-time flexibility and autonomy (Lott, 2015). Gröpel and Kuhl (2009) in their study looked at correlation among different WLB variables which includes: intimacy, sociability/separation, acceptance, altruism, receiving help, approval, status, autonomy/dependence (autonomy here refers to an individual's ability to set working hours and place), performance/failure, control, understanding, sense of meaning, excitement, trust in oneself/embarrassment, and self-reward (Gröpel & Kuhl, 2009). Therefore, autonomy can be placed under both temporal and spatial flexibilities. Unsocial working hour, which is also another WLB variable, can be placed under temporal flexibility. Anttila et al. (2015) also considered 'Autonomy' as an important WLB variable in (Anttila et al., 2015). For the purpose of this study, only autonomy is included since it is not only a variable affecting WLB but also reflective of temporal and spatial flexibilities.

2.5 Individual WLB Strategy

Human beings are irreplaceable, proactive and possess the capability of guiding their own locus of control by reshaping several parameters and activities in ways which bear meaning at both home and work (Clark, 2000; Zheng et al., 2015). Greenhaus and Powell (2006), in their Work – family enrichment theory, argued that people obtain a number of resources and skills as they cross borders between family and life on a daily basis. A list of these skills include several psychological, physical, social-capital, flexible and material resources and these often cover a number of task related cognitive, interpersonal and multitasking skills necessary for both work and life enrichment (Greenhaus & Powell, 2006; Zheng et al., 2015). For the purpose of this study, a 6-item individual WLB strategy, reflecting the aforementioned items, is used.

2.6 Organizational WLB Strategy

The systems approach of WLB strategy gives an idea about what an organization can do in order to offer a balance between work and life of its employees (Bird, 2006). Bird (2006) also argued that both individual and work-related strategies are equally important for work-life balance of the working individuals (Bird, 2006). Therefore, it can be concluded that list of individual skills, capabilities and organizational strategies such as: reducing emphasis on time at work and/or, flexitime, notice for overtime, part-time work, job sharing, reducing working hours, townships, celebrating festivals, bring your family to your workplace, travel as incentive, movies, cultural, sports and recreational events, yoga clubs, volunteering to encourage employees and their families to address social issues, transport facility child care center, child schooling, leave provisions, peer support, supervisory support, eldercare facilities and maternity benefits are found in different literatures as organizational WLB policies (Aluwihare-Samaranayake et al., 2018; Baral et al., 2011; Chandra, 2012; Ilsøe et al., 2017; Tasnim et al., 2017; Uddin et al., 2013; Zheng et al., 2015). In this study, organizational WLB strategy is developed based on these aforementioned variables culminating into a 21 item construct.

2.7 Measuring WLB

Work-Life Balance variable has been measured in different ways in different studies based on the demand and nature of the study. For example, Antai et al. (2015) has considered WLB as a dichotomous variable and their responses were dichotomized as either good or poor. The question which they asked was, “In general, do your working hours fit in with your family or social commitments outside work?” (Antai et al., 2015). Mathew and Panchanatham (2011) have measured WLB using a 5 point likert scale based on a statement used in Wong and Ko (2009) (Mathew & Panchanatham, 2011; Wong & Ko, 2009). The statement is: “I am having a satisfactory level of work-life balance” (Mathew and Panchanatham, p. 85, 2011). One literature also measured work-life balance enhancer using a combination of multiple factors, such as: approach of problem solving used at job which had also been proved to be effective in home-domain, strategies used at work which had also been proved to be effective for an individual to be a better parent as well as spouse (Singh, 2014).

Wong and Ko’s (2009) question was used as a guideline for this study. As mentioned earlier, this question tends to identify the status of an individual’s work-life balance. 4, instead of 6 items, of this question are used in this research due to repetitive contents.

2.8 Subjective Wellbeing (SWB)

Subjective wellbeing (SWB) reflects the degree to which an individual considers himself/herself satisfied with his/her life (Gröpel & Kuhl, 2009). It is the cognitive component of SWB. Gröpel and Kuhl (2009) also used the concept of SWB to determine positive and negative moods of individuals and termed these together as the affective component of SWB (Gröpel & Kuhl, 2009). Following are the variables used in this study to determine affective component of Bangladeshi garment workers’ SWB:

Positive Mood: *happy, joyful, pleased, and confident*

Negative Mood: *sad, depressed, frustrated, and anxious (Gröpel & Kuhl, 2009; Quirin et al., 2009)*

For determining the status of the cognitive component of SWB, however, a five-item construct called the Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWLS) had been used (Diener et al., 1985). The items were scored using a 7 point likert scale with 1 being highly dissatisfied and 7 being highly satisfied. In addition and also contradiction to the prior studies, this study wants to see how the affective component of SWB affects the cognitive component of the SWB. Because, it is only rational to posit that an individual’s emotional expression will certainly affect his/her perception of happiness in life. Moreover, this breakdown will help us to identify how individual variables of this study create an emotional response in individuals. In addition, if the results prove that the affective component of SWB affects SWLS, it will also help us to segregate perceptual response of an individual about his/her own degree of satisfaction with life from the work and family related events for creating a certain emotional expression. The intention to test the aforesaid dependency is in line with the findings from Nzeku

& Duffett (2021). They found that cognitive attitude positively influences affective attitudes for tourists (Nzeku & Duffett, 2021). The construct of attitude is universally used in many disciplines starting from education ending up to consumer behavior (Fazio et al., 1989; Scanlon et al., 2022). In view of this universality of the attitude construct, it is expected that the influence of the cognitive component on the affective component of SWB will be positive and significant.

3. HYPOTHESES

3.1 Null Hypotheses

H01: *There is no association present among duration, timing, tempo, autonomy, spatial flexibility, role conflict, and interactions among individual and organizational WLB policies, and WLB of RMG workers of Bangladesh.*

H02: *Individual WLB strategies do not affect WLB of RMG workers of Bangladesh.*

H03: *There is no association present among duration, timing, tempo, autonomy, spatial flexibility, role conflict, WLB, SWLS, and interactions among individual and organizational WLB and SWB of Bangladeshi Garments workers.*

Ha1: *Duration, timing, tempo, autonomy, spatial flexibility, role conflict, and interactions among individual and organizational WLB policies significantly affect WLB of Bangladeshi RMG workers.*

Ha2: *All individual WLB strategies significantly affect WLB of RMG workers of Bangladesh.*

Ha3: *Duration, timing, tempo, autonomy, spatial flexibility, role conflict, WLB, SWLS, and interactions among individual and organizational WLB significantly affect SWB of Bangladeshi Garments workers.*

Hasan et al. (2017) studied overall wellbeing of RMG workers and considered WLB as one of the components of it. However, the complex dynamics of the WLB variable itself and subjective wellbeing of the workers were not studied. Asadullah & Talukder (2019) tried to identify SWB of the RMG workers without segregating the cognitive aspect from the affective aspects. They found that WLB enhances SWB. But, they did not attempt to determine how workers' beliefs or, preconception about their lives affect the affective component of SWB. Moreover, their main purpose was to individually identify pecuniary and non-pecuniary aspects of SWB, not the job and work aspect of SWB (Asadullah & Talukder, 2019). SWB in the context of urban dweller was measured by Mahmud & Sawada (2018). However, their primary interest was to determine how environment affect SWB, not WLB (Mahmud & Sawada, 2018). Tarafder (2020), in her PhD thesis, tried to deepen the concept of Employee Wellbeing (EWB) from a developing country perspective. Her study also targeted Bangladeshi RMG workers. However, she did not try to determine overall satisfaction of RMG workers with their lives and neither did she determine how satisfactions with life of the RMG workers affect SWB (Tarafder, 2020). In a

nutshell, this study is addressing a number of gaps in the existing literature. They are: (a) determining overall status of affective SWB, SWL (cognitive SWB), and overall WLB status of Bangladeshi RMG workers, (b) determining the role that cognitive component of SWB and WLB plays to predict affective SWB of Bangladeshi RMG workers, and (c) identify how interactions between organizational and individual WLB strategies affect workers' SWB and overall WLB status in the RMG sector of the country. Additionally, the interaction effect of individual and organization WLB on WLB and SWB has also not been tested. Furthermore, no one, to the best of our knowledge and search of literature, has tried to identify which individual WLB strategy affects WLB the most. This research is going to focus on these issues, too.

3.2 Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 : Conceptual Framework [The dotted boxes correspond to the predictors and predicted variables related to WLB. The dotted lines reflect the direction of causality. Solid lines and boxes, on the contrary, show the direction of causality and variables related to the affective component of SWB respectively.]

4. METHODOLOGY

This is a confirmatory research in the sense that this research wants to test a few hypotheses related to WLB and SWB of garments workers of Bangladesh (Zikmund, 2003). A primary survey was conducted on a selected sample of garment workers and their responses had been recorded using a 5 point Likert scale (except for the SWB and WLB components, scoring mechanism for these had been discussed earlier). Some of the questions were set in reverse order for which reverse scoring had been used. Ordinary Least Square (OLS) is used to determine associations among different variables of the study. STATA was used for data analysis.

4.1 Sampling Method and Type

It was found in Shahajada Mia and Masrufa Akter (2019) that about 4 million workers are directly employed in RMG sector of the country (Shahajada Mia & Masrufa Akter, 2019). For the purpose of the study, purposive sampling method has been chosen and 241 samples from different ready-made garments and textile firms were taken. The formula to calculate sample size is, $n = N * X / (X + N - 1)$, where, $X = Z_{\alpha/2}^2 * p * (1-p) / MOE^2$ (Daniel & Cross, 2018).

Here, n = sample size, $Z_{\alpha/2}$ is the critical value of Normal distribution at $\alpha/2$, MOE = margin of Error, p = sample proportion (assumed to be 0.5 for getting maximum value for a given population). Therefore, sample size for this study at 5% margin of error = 385 and for 10% margin of error = 68. Initially targeted sample size was 385, but only 241 could be reached. Calculation shows that 241 as a sample size is standard for a 6.05% margin of error, which is pretty close to 5%.

The Bangladesh Garment Manufacturers and Exporters Association (BGMEA) indicate that there are 4,000+ garments factories in Bangladesh (BGMEA, 2022). In several earlier studies, researchers have taken samples from around 20 RMG firms to conduct their studies (Alam & Dhamija, 2022; Marium Akter, 2018; Rubel & Kee, 2014). Following their footprint, samples were collected from 20 large RMG companies due to time, resource and access related limitations. In view of the acceptability of the prior research and availability of responses from 241 respondents, it can be confidently concluded that the sample size is representative of the ground realities for the RMG sector of the country.

4.2 Quantitative Models

For the purpose of the study the following OLS models will be used:

Model 1

$$WLB_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 DUR_i + \beta_2TIMING_i + \beta_3TEMPO_i+ \beta_4 AUTONOMY_i + \beta_5SPATIAL_FLEX_i + \beta_6ROLE_CONFLICT_i + \beta_7INDWLB_i * ORGWLB_i + \epsilon_i \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Model 2

$$WLB_j = \delta_0 + \delta_1 AO_j + \delta_2AP_j + \delta_3AQ_j + \delta_4AR_j + \delta_5AS_j + \delta_6 AT_j + \theta_j \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Model 3

$$SWB_k = \gamma_0 + \gamma_1DUR_k + \gamma_2TIMING_k + \gamma_3TEMPO_i + \gamma_4AUTONOMY_k + \gamma_5SPATIAL_FLEX_k + \gamma_6ROLE_CONFLICT_k + \gamma_7WLB_j + \gamma_8SWLS_k + \gamma_9INDWLB_k * ORGWLB_k + \mu_k \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

[$\alpha, \delta, \gamma, \mu = Intercept terms, \epsilon, \theta, \mu = Error terms, \beta, \delta, \gamma = Coefficients$]

In case of the presence of Heteroskedasticity, OLS with robust standard errors is applied.

Operationalizing of the Variables

Table A1 of the appendix show the operationalization of the aforementioned variables.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive analyses show that (please see tables A4 – A7) RMG workers of Bangladesh possess Neutral Positive mood and High Negative mood. In other words, they are unhappy. The WLB scores show that RMG workers’ WLB is Moderate. However, most importantly, the workers’ cognitive component of wellbeing or, beliefs

about satisfaction with life is Low. If WLB cannot be improved and individuals' satisfaction with lives cannot be changed, aggressive outbursts or, other negative and extreme emotional response is imminent.

To test the relationship presented in equation (1), Ordinary Least Square (OLS) was applied first (Please see Table A2 of the appendix). However, Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg test for Heteroskedasticity proves that there is Heteroskedasticity present in the model. Therefore, OLS with robust standard errors have been used. The R-squared of the regression Table 1(a) confirms that the model can explain around 95.46% variations in WLB. Autonomy has the highest negative impact on WLB and is also significant at 1%. It indicates that the autonomy to set rosters for duty reduces WLB of Bangladeshi RMG workers. It is contrary to the findings of most literature (Grzywacz & Marks, 2000). However, negative relationship between these two variables is not unfounded in other countries (as shown earlier). It is possible that the autonomy to set own schedule of duty increases their tendency to exert more efforts to work (Anttila et al., 2015; Kelliher & Anderson, 2008). This may cause disruptions in the balance between work and life. Among the rest of the variables, Tempo has the highest significant positive impact on WLB ($p < 0.01$). This finding is well in line with existing literature. The same is true for Timing. The Interaction between individual and organizational WLB strategies was also found to enhance WLB indicating the fact that supportive policies from the organization added with appropriate planning from an individual can improve his/her WLB score. However, Spatial Flexibility and Duration do not have significant effect on WLB. This is contrary to the initial prediction and findings from prior literature (Anttila et al., 2015). Table 1(b) shows regression results for all of the aforementioned variables except for the Interaction term and includes Individual as well as Organizational WLB as individual variables. The results reflect that Individual WLB is an insignificant predictor of WLB. However, Organizational WLB policy has significant impact on WLB of the workers. The nature of significance of other variables is similar to those in Table 1(a) except for Spatial Flexibility. In Table 1(b), Spatial Flexibility is shown to have a marginal significance at 10%. It is also important to mention here that the degrees of significance of the variables in Table 1(b) are slightly different from those of Table 1(a). In short, the findings from the comparison of Table 1(a) and 1(b) show that Interaction between individual and organizational WLB is a significant predictor of WLB despite the fact that Individual WLB is insignificant. Therefore, if organizations do not have appropriate WLB policies, despite taking individual strategies to balance work and life commitments, workers will fail to attain their objectives.

Table 1(a) : Robust Regression

<i>DEPENDENT VARIABLES</i>			
WLB			
<i>INDEPENDENT VARIABLES</i>	COEF.	ROBUST STANDARD ERROR	T
DUR	-0.1243301 (0.322)	0.1252537	-0.99
TIMING	0.0815596* (0.085)	0.047114	1.73
TEMPO	0.6809055*** (0.000)	0.1068151	6.37
AUTONOMY	-0.7716906*** (0.000)	0.1283752	-6.01
SPATIAL_FLEX	0.1103612 (0.824)	0.4965766	0.22
ROLE_CONFLICT	0.2869106*** (0.000)	0.0387131	7.41
INDWLB*ORGWLB	0.0067976*** (0.000)	0.001798	3.78
CONSTANT	-7.625276*** (0.000)	1.661032	-4.59

Prob > F= 0.0000, R-squared = 0.9546,

*** Significant at 1%, ** Significant at 5%, *Significant at 10%, p values in parentheses

Table 1(b) : Robust Regression without interaction term

<i>DEPENDENT VARIABLES</i>			
WLB			
<i>INDEPENDENT VARIABLES</i>	COEF.	ROBUST STANDARD ERROR	T
DUR	0.0019616 (0.978)	0.0710186	0.03
TIMING	-0.4034763*** (0.000)	0.1136627	-3.55
TEMPO	0.4480153*** (0.000)	0.1085651	4.13
AUTONOMY	-0.39439*** (0.008)	0.146536	-2.69

SPATIAL_FLEX	0.4623441* (0.100)	0.2796582	1.65
ROLE_CONFLICT	0.1654565*** (0.000)	0.0463749	3.57
INDWLB	0.0518809 (0.592)	0.0966368	0.54
ORGWLB	0.2898911*** (0.000)	0.0450706	6.43
CONSTANT	-10.79968*** (0.000)	2.92033	-3.70

Prob > F = 0.0000, R-squared = 0.9739,

*** Significant at 1%, ** Significant at 5%, *Significant at 10%, p values in parentheses

To understand which individual WLB strategies are better, regression was run with WLB being the dependent variable and individual strategies as the independent ones equation (2). Findings suggest that the ability to meet community commitments and sharing childcare facilities have significant positive influence on WLB (Table 2). This finding is also in line with prior literature (Greenhaus & Powell, 2006; Zheng et al., 2015). It is important to mention here that Hofstede's study on cultural dimension confirms Bangladesh to be a collective society (Bernard et al., 2022; Robbins & Judge, 2015). Therefore, it is obvious that community commitments are significantly important in collective culture. As mentioned in Quynh (2021), collectivism in a society creates an expectation among individuals that their family members will look after them in need (Quynh, 2021). Collectivism can therefore be offered as a plausible explanation for the above relationship. However, capability to manage stressful situation and ability to meet lifestyle commitments has significant negative influence on WLB. This is completely opposite of the suggestions of prior literature (Greenhaus & Powell, 2006; Zheng et al., 2015).

Table 2 : Robust Regression for Ind. WLB Strategies and WLB

<i>DEPENDENT VARIABLES</i>			
WLB			
<i>INDEPENDENT VARIABLES</i>	COEF.	ROBUST STANDARD ERROR	T
AO	-0.2290943 (0.900)	1.819396	-0.13
AP	-3.825504*** (0.000)	0.291079	-13.14
AQ	0.879584 (0.728)	2.526865	0.35

AR	1.130023** (0.024)	0.4960204	2.28
AS	-1.9027*** (0.000)	0.4113004	-4.63
AT	2.068243*** (0.000)	0.2033338	10.17
CONSTANT	16.11231*** (0.000)	1.972899	8.17

Prob > F = 0.0000, R-squared = 0.9290

*** Significant at 1%, ** Significant at 5%, *Significant at 10%, p values in parentheses

[AO = Maintaining a positive outlook, AP = Capability to Manage stressful situation, AQ = Arranging times to help others, AR = Sharing childcare responsibilities with parents/spouse/other family members, AS = Ability to meet lifestyle commitments, AT = Ability to fulfill community commitments]

Robust regression is also used to determine how WLB variables, WLB itself and cognitive component of wellbeing affect the affective component of wellbeing of RMG workers in the country (3). Table 3 shows that SWL of an individual (Cognitive component of SWB) has the highest positive and significant effect on the affective wellbeing of the workers followed by Autonomy. It indicates that the beliefs of the workers about one's own satisfaction with life along with freedom to set his/her own roster make the person happy in his/her life. Role conflict is found to have a negative relationship with affective SWB. These findings offer valuable insights to the research community and practitioners to design appropriate stimuli to bring a positive emotional response in the RMG workers' lives.

Internal consistency or, reliability of all composite scales have been determined and summarized in Table A2. Except for Tempo, Spatial Flexibility and Affective SWB, all other scales have acceptable Cronbach's Alphas (close to 0.6 or, above). However, keeping these constructs in line with the suggestions of existing literature is important since identification factors for the items are beyond the scope of this study and can be taken as individual investigations by themselves. The VIF values of models 1, 2 and 3 are 5.09, 9.63 and 11.74 respectively. Only model 3 has marginally higher VIF than the rule of thumb 10. However, they are well within 30. Therefore, it can be concluded that multicollinearity problems for the models are not significant concerns as this is between 10 and 30 indicating weak multicollinearity (Peduzzi et al., 2012). Earlier research also shows that even high multicollinearity may not be a problem unless the standard error is high (Alin, 2010). In this study, the standard error is rather small nullifying the possibility of any serious consequences of weak collinearity for the concerned Model (Model 3).

Table 3 : Robust Regression Output

DEPENDENT VARIABLES			
SWB			
INDEPENDENT VARIABLES	COEF.	ROBUST STANDARD ERROR	T
DUR	0.076782 (0.380)	0.087302	0.88
TIMING	0.063337 (0.202)	0.049473	1.28
TEMPO	0.01382 (0.924)	0.145493	0.09
AUTONOMY	0.251122* (0.070)	0.138117	1.82
SPATIAL_FLEX	-0.24556 (0.424)	0.306721	-0.8
ROLE_CONFLICT	-0.27541*** (0.000)	0.073173	-3.76
WLB	0.2271931 (0.221)	0.1849824	1.23
SWLS	0.342823** (0.003)	0.113986	3.01
INDWLB*ORGWLB	-0.00119 (0.580)	0.00215	-0.55
CONSTANT	29.87024*** (0.000)	2.602522	11.48

Prob > F = 0.0000, R-squared = 0.4788

*** Significant at 1%, ** Significant at 5%, *Significant at 10%, p values in parentheses

In summary, it can be said that that the interaction of individual and organizational WLB is insignificant to improve happiness of the RMG workers. But, a few organizational policies are. Moreover, a few individual WLB strategies improve the balance between work and life of the respondents, but that does not affect their subjective wellbeing. Additionally, role conflict reduces workers' SWB. Despite the fact that spatial flexibility, timing and tempo affect WLB, they neither directly nor indirectly affect SWB. Therefore, instead on focusing on all individual WLB variables, specific focus on autonomy and organizational WLB policies (a list of which is already given in the literature review section on this study) will be more effective to make RMG workers happy in their lives. It is, however, important to remember that policy measures are also necessary to turn negative cognitive beliefs about a worker's satisfaction with life to positive beliefs. This complex dynamics must be closely studied by RMG managers to identify the specific policy that they

must adopt for offering a better organizational experience to their workers in a Bangladeshi context. Similarly, the RMG workers can also learn about the meaningful WLB strategies they need to adopt in order to improve their overall satisfaction with life and happiness.

6. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

Interaction between Subjective wellbeing and Work-life balance is severely under-researched. This paper looks at several dimensions of Work-Life Balance (WLB), Subjective Wellbeing (SWB), individual WLB strategies (INDWLB), Organizational Work-Life Balance (ORGWLB) and satisfaction with life (SWLS) of the RMG workers of Bangladesh. The findings suggest that positive and significant relationship exists among (a) *Timing*, (b) *Tempo*, (c) *Role Conflict*, (d) *Interaction between individual and organizational WLB* and (e) *overall WLB of the RMG workers of Bangladesh*. However, individual WLB strategies do not significantly affect WLB. This finding offers new knowledge about the RMG workers of Bangladesh implying the fact that organizational policies and individual strategies can collectively improve WLB in the RMG sectors of the country. Moreover, role conflict's positive association with WLB, a contrary evidence with literature as mentioned earlier, may indicate that a certain level of role conflict is probably assumed by the RMG workers as an expected phenomenon. However, detailed research is warranted to understand the reason for this relationship. In addition to this, affective Subjective Wellbeing (SWB) of the RMG workers has been found to be positively enhanced by (a) *workers' beliefs about his/her own satisfaction with life*, and (b) *autonomy to set his/her own roster*. However, role conflict does not make the workers happy, as measured by the affective SWB score. This is also another interesting knowledge about the SWB of the RMG workers in the country. Because, role conflict positively influences WLB but negatively influences happiness. Therefore, caution is needed to set appropriate policies to both improve WLB and happiness of the RMG workers of the country.

Earlier research works do not indicate the level of happiness of Bangladeshi RMG workers, their overall WLB status and Satisfaction with Life. This gap is also filled by this study. The findings of this research implies that Bangladeshi workers (in the RMG and textile sectors) are unhappy, enjoys moderate WLB and do not believe that they are satisfied with their lives. This is detrimental for the wellbeing of the workers and puts the country behind as far as achieving SDG 8, or, offering an environment of 'decent work' is concerned.

6.1 Future Research Directions

Contrary to earlier researches in this field, this study also attempts to identify the effectiveness of each individual WLB strategy to improve overall WLB status of individual workers of the RMG sector of the country. Findings, as mentioned above, suggest that an individual's capability to share childcare responsibilities with family members and meet community commitments positively affect WLB. However, ability to manage stressful situation and meeting lifestyle commitments has negative

relationship with WLB. The latter findings imply that greater inability to manage stress and meet all of the lifestyle requirements can better balance RMG workers' works and lives. One reason for such a finding may be the fact that the RMG workers are unaware of the sources, effects and ways to manage stress in their lives. Therefore, they have taken it for granted that to balance work and life, stress is inevitable. In addition, they may have found that improving WLB requires sacrificing fulfillment of their lifestyle requirements. These findings have certainly opened a door for additional and detailed qualitative research in this field to better understand the sources, effects, and remedies for the current state of mindset, inabilities, and ignorance of the RMG workers. It is also to be noted here that collective insignificance of the individual WLB strategies and higher significance of a few individual WLB strategies has also opened avenues for further research.

As far as policy directions are concerned, this research dictates that (a) *spatial flexibility is irrelevant as a WLB policy*, (b) *individual WLB strategies need to be revisited*, (c) *psychological training and counseling must be offered to corporate houses as well as individual households to improve both cognitive and affective SWB*, (d) *organizations must set effective WLB policies to improve WLB and happiness of their employees*, (e) *national level projects need to be undertaken to assess affective and cognitive SWBs of workers of different sectors and identify sectoral solutions to offer a countrywide enabling environment to all Bangladeshi employees for achieving SDG 8*. In addition to these, Bangladeshi organizations must ensure that their HR policies effectively acknowledge the needs for psychological, career and lifestyle counseling in order to ensure decent works at the micro level and to improve overall wellbeing of their workers at the macro level of the country. Collective efforts to ensure better SWB of the workers will help the RMG firms to comply with and exceed international guidelines set for them and snatch recognitions from their national and international clients as humane organizations in an emerging economy like Bangladesh. It is high time that this sector understands the importance of exceeding basic compliance to improve their organization performance and sustainability as a whole.

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APPENDIX

Table A1 : Variables of the study

Model	Independent Variables	Dependent Variables
Model 1	WLB_i = Work – Life Balance	DUR _{i/k} = Duration TIMING _{i/k} = Timing TEMPO _{i/k} = Tempo AUTONOMY _{i/k} = Autonomy SPATIAL_FLEX _{i/k} = Spatial Flexibility ROLE_CONFLICT _{i/k} = Role Conflict INDWLB _{i/k} *ORGWLB _{i/k} = Interaction between individual and organizational WLB
Model 2	WLB_j = Work – Life Balance	AO _j = Maintaining a positive outlook AP _j = Capability to Manage stressful situation AQ _j = Arranging times to help others AR _j = Sharing childcare responsibilities with parents/spouse/other family members AS _j = Ability to meet lifestyle commitments AT _j = Ability to fulfill community commitments
Model 3	SWB_k = Affective component of Subjective Wellbeing	DUR _k = Duration TIMING _k = Timing TEMPO _k = Tempo AUTONOMY _k = Autonomy SPATIAL_FLEX _k = Spatial Flexibility ROLE_CONFLICT _k = Role Conflict INDWLB _k * ORGWLB _k = Interaction between individual and organizational WLB SWLS _k = Satisfaction with life scale reflecting an individual's perception about his/her satisfaction with life (Affective components of SWB)
<i>i, j, k = i, j and k – th individual</i>		

Table A2 : Internal Consistency

Scale	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
WLB	0.8107	4
ORGANIZATIONAL WLB	0.9220	21
INDIVIDUAL WLB	0.8002	6
ROLE CONFLICT	0.8912	15
SPATIAL FLEXIBILITY	0.1176	2
AUTONOMY	0.7154	4
TEMPO	0.2431	4
TIMING	0.8395	4
DURATION	0.8502	3
TOTAL_SWB	0.3006	9
SWLS	0.5820	5

Table A3 : SWLS = Satisfaction With Life Scale (Cognitive) (Diener et al., 1985)

1 (Highly dissatisfied)	2 (Moderately Dissatisfied)	3 (Slightly Dissatisfied)	4 (Neutral)	5 (Slightly satisfied)	6 (Moderately Satisfied)	7 (Highly Satisfied)
In most ways my life is close to my ideal.						
The conditions of my life are excellent.						
I am satisfied with my life						
So far I have gotten the important things I want in life						
If I could live my life over, I would change almost nothing						

Table A4 :

SWB Affective: Positive Mood (1= Strongly Disagree, 5= Strongly Agree)

Score	Happy	Joyful	Active	Pleased	Confident
1	0.63%	4.17%	32.26%	0%	10.2%
2	65.82%	45.83%	42.74%	65.63%	52.38%
3	24.05%	33.33%	2.42%	33.75%	0.68%
4	9.49%	16.67%	20.97%	0.63%	36.73%
5	0%	0%	1.61%	0%	0%
Weighted Average Score	2.42	2.63	2.17	2.35	2.6392
Interpretation	Neutral	Neutral	Neutral	Neutral	Neutral
Overall: Neutral Positive Mood					

Table A5 :
SWB Affective: Negative Mood (1= Strongly Disagree, 5= Strongly Agree)

Score	Sad	Depressed	Frustrated	Anxious
1	0%	0%	0.65%	0%
2	35.21%	0%	9.74%	0%
3	0%	0%	38.96%	0%
4	64.79%	99.14%	34.42%	37.89%
5	0%	0.86%	16.23%	62.11%
<i>Weighted Average Score</i>	<i>3.2958</i>	<i>4.0086</i>	<i>3.5584</i>	<i>4.6211</i>
<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Agree</i>	<i>Strongly Agree</i>	<i>Agree</i>	<i>Strongly Agree</i>
Overall: High Negative Mood				

Table A6 : WLB status of RMG workers of Bangladesh

WLB	Count	Weight	Weighted Score
6	28	11.62%	0.6972
7	1	0.41%	0.0287
8	43	17.84%	1.4272
9	1	0.41%	0.0369
11	1	0.41%	0.0451
12	15	6.22%	0.7464
14	27	11.20%	1.568
TOTAL	242	100%	12.8321
Moderate WLB			
Range:			
Lowest WLB	4		
Low WLB	4 – 12		
Moderate WLB	13 – 16		
High WLB	17 – 23		
Highest WLB	24		

Table A7 : SWLS

SWLS	Freq.	Percent	Weighted Score	
7	15	6.25%	0.43750	
8	20	8.33%	0.66640	
9	30	12.50%	1.12500	
10	23	9.58%	0.95800	
11	2	0.83%	0.09130	
14	2	0.83%	0.11620	
15	3	1.25%	0.18750	
17	17	7.08%	1.20360	
18	101	42.08%	7.57440	
19	14	5.83%	1.10770	
20	2	0.83%	0.16600	
21	11	4.58%	0.96180	
Total	240	1.00	14.60	
Low SWL				

Range:
 Lowest SWLS: 5
 Low SWLS: 5 – 15
 Neutral: 16 – 20
 High SWLS: 21 – 34
 Highest SWLS: 35

Table A8 : Correlations Matrix for items of Social Support

	DUR	TIMING	TEMPO	AUTONOMY	SPATIAL_FLEX	ROLE_CONFLICT	INDWLB	ORGWLB	WLB	SWB	SWLS
DUR	1										
TIMING	0.6842*** (0.000)	1									
TEMPO	-0.1866*** (0.0037)	-0.3142*** (0.000)	1								
AUTONOMY	0.1458** (0.0236)	-0.2402*** (0.0002)	0.4159*** (0.000)	1							
SPATIAL_FLEX	0.8734*** (0.000)	0.7296*** (0.000)	-0.2793*** (0.000)	0.1662*** (0.0098)	1						
ROLE_CONFLICT	0.8028*** (0.000)	0.7388*** (0.000)	-0.2975*** (0.000)	0.283*** (0.000)	0.8777*** (0.000)	1					
INDWLB	-0.2867*** (0.000)	-0.7154*** (0.000)	0.1573** (0.0145)	0.183*** (0.0044)	-0.3566*** (0.000)	-0.5415*** (0.000)	1				
ORGWLB	0.5776*** (0.000)	0.9289*** (0.000)	-0.3223*** (0.000)	-0.4679*** (0.000)	0.5971*** (0.000)	0.595*** (0.000)	-0.6497*** (0.000)	1			
WLB	0.652*** (0.000)	0.8736*** (0.000)	-0.2662*** (0.000)	-0.3962*** (0.000)	0.6761*** (0.000)	0.6624*** (0.000)	-0.5901*** (0.000)	0.9573*** (0.000)	1		
SWB	-0.1911*** (0.0029)	-0.0481 (0.4572)	0.2189*** (0.0006)	-0.3968*** (0.000)	-0.2665*** (0.000)	-0.3784*** (0.000)	0.0863 (0.182)	0.0803 (0.2143)	0.1074* (0.0964)	1	
SWLS	0.7679*** (0.000)	0.8321*** (0.000)	-0.3158*** (0.000)	-0.1661*** (0.0099)	0.8175*** (0.000)	0.8217*** (0.000)	-0.562*** (0.000)	0.8095*** (0.000)	0.9*** (0.000)	-0.0115 (0.8599)	1

*** Significant at 1%, ** Significant at 5%, * Significant at 10%